

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th October 2021

Accepted: 25th October 2021

Online: 30th October 2021

KEY WORDS

*information technology,
pedagogical research,
uniform education,
system everywhere*

PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF TRAINING OF SMALL SPECIALISTS FOR SMALL ENTERPRISES AND DOMESTIC SERVICES

Khusanova Mavluda Nuriddinovna

asistant, Department of Chemistry, Namangan Institute of
Engineering and Technology, Republic of UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5651436>

ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the preparation of professional areas in the teaching of chemistry in higher education, which opens up opportunities for development and improvement of the field

Introduction. The reason for our pedagogical research and observations on the subject, object and subject of research is that at all stages of social development, the village and its people fully preserve the spiritual and cultural values of certain nations and peoples, but the city embraces the cultural and educational views of different nationalities. differs from the infrastructure. The peculiarities of the rural conditions of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, are also important because the productive forces and their growth differ in many respects from the same features of the city. In particular, the pace of socio-economic and cultural development is closely linked with the demographic characteristics of centuries-old traditions. When thinking about the social status of training of junior specialists in our country,

first of all, we need to emphasize the following.

Main part. For a long time, the training of qualified personnel for all sectors of the economy in our country was carried out on the basis of instructions and standards issued by the center, the specifics of each of the former Soviet republics were almost ignored.

The end result of this process was, first, that all means of production were considered to be the sole public property of the former Soviet Union, that all members of society were socially "equal, classless social order," and that a single Soviet promotion of the idea of the people, based on the development of socio-economic development of society on a transnational basis, the elimination of the gap between urban and rural areas is based on formality;

Second, the establishment of a uniform education system everywhere, regardless of urban and rural infrastructure, the conduct of communist (general) policy in all areas, the political factor of equalization of all areas;

Thirdly, the shortcomings in the organization of vocational education, including the fact that vocational schools are organized mainly in cities, the need to train personnel for urban and rural agriculture, discrimination against national crafts.

This factor was a moral condition that caused a number of problems in the vocational training of rural youth. Although the strengthening of socialist ideology in the minds of the people through the media and the press, the principles of socialist morality - collectivism, the determination of the ideas of internationalism, respect for national and spiritual heritage of peoples in program documents, attention to their study, their use in education in practice it was the opposite, the advanced aspects of the national-cultural heritage were not used. Instead of a national culture, a common Soviet culture was formed for almost all peoples - Russian, Fapb culture. In particular, Uzbekistan has a bad attitude to the construction of world historical and national architectural monuments, folk arts and crafts, weaving, sewing, public services and catering, recreation, which support the historical significance of rural weaving and sewing. For example, in many villages, cultural facilities such as teahouses and guzars began to disappear.

Results and discussion. The above situation also had a negative impact on the content and method of education, with the

introduction of 11 years of compulsory general, secondary education for all children. Factors such as ignoring their interests and abilities in sending them to the profession, treating the child as an object of upbringing rather than a subject, and formality in assessing the spirituality and activism of the student have damaged the reputation of national culture and crafts. That is why many young people, especially those living in rural areas, have started to make it their main goal to go to the cities, graduate from higher and secondary special educational institutions and stay and work in the cities. This, in turn, led to a violation of the principle of rational use of labor on the ground, that is, at a time when there is a shortage of manpower in one region, there is a shortage of jobs for specialists in another.

Until now, it was considered that the main purpose of training for all sectors of production was only the formation of professional skills. This factor was the basis for the development of curricula and programs of higher and secondary special educational institutions, vocational schools. Therefore, a trained specialist could be a good engineer in his chosen specialty, someone who knows the secrets of technology, but did not have enough skills to apply this knowledge and skills where, when and how. As a result, the specialist was used inefficiently. Under the former Soviet regime, the principle of training under the guise of pre-planning was grossly violated, and personnel were trained without taking into account regional needs. Data on the total number of trained and educated specialists were considered to be very positive changes in the country. At the same time, it should be noted that these

“achievements” have not always been sufficiently exploited, indifference to social wealth such as knowledge and skills of the specialist, indifference to him, use of personnel only on the basis of diploma often led to disappointments. Therefore, the issue of admission to higher and secondary special educational institutions, directing students to choose a profession, their rational use remains a very pressing issue. To address the above-mentioned problems, the Law "On the National Program of Personnel Training" was adopted, the purpose of which is to "radically reform the education system, to completely rid it of ideological views and deviations from the past, meeting high moral and ethical standards in developed democracies." is to create a national system of training highly qualified personnel.

Conclusions. The purpose of these official documents is to radically reform the education system, to rid it of the ideological views and stereotypes of the past, to create a national system of training highly qualified personnel that meets the highest moral and ethical standards at the level of developed democracies. Achieving this goal involves solving the following tasks:

- Reform of the education system in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education"; to ensure the consistent development of the education system as a single educational and scientific-production complex on the basis of the formation of a competitive environment in the field of education and training of state and non-state educational institutions;

- Adaptation of the education and training system to the ongoing processes of modernization of society, the development of a developed democratic state governed by the rule of law;
- Providing training institutions with highly qualified specialists, raising the prestige and social status of pedagogical activity;
- Review of the system and content of training based on the prospects of social and economic development of the country, the needs of society, modern achievements in science, culture, engineering and technology;
- Development and introduction of effective forms and methods of spiritual and moral education and enlightenment of students;
- Introduction of an objective system of quality assessment of education and training, certification and accreditation of educational institutions;
- Creation of a regulatory, logistical and information base that ensures the required level and quality of education in the new socio-economic conditions, the priority of the system of training in practice and guarantees of sustainable development;
- Ensuring the effective integration of education, science and industry, the development of mechanisms for the formation of state requirements for the number and quality of trained personnel, as well as the orders of non-governmental structures, enterprises and organizations

References:

1. Mamajanovna, E. R. (2020). MODERN-INNOVATIVE MECHANISMS OF TEACHING CHEMISTRY IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND THE ESSENCE OF THEIR CONTENT. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 5(Special Issue), 3-3.
2. Khoshimov, F. F., Egamberdieva, R., & Fayzullaeva, M. F. (2020). PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE UZBEKISTAN-JAPANESE EDUCATION SYSTEM. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 5(Special Issue), 4-4. 5.
3. Эгамбердиева, Р. (2021). Application of innovative technologies in teaching chemistry in higher education. *Обществоиинновации*, 2(3/S), 316-319.
4. Khoshimov, F. F., Egamberdieva, R., & Fayzullaeva, M. F. (2020). PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE UZBEKISTAN-JAPANESE EDUCATION SYSTEM. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(9), 342-347. 7.
5. Xoshimov, F. F., & Fayzullaeva, M. F. (2019, October). Japanese experience in education system development. In Conference "Innovative ideas in improving chemistry, food and chemical technologies", NamMTI.
6. Khoshimov, F. F., & Fayzullaeva, M. F. (2019, October). Uzbek and Chinese education systems: similarities and differences in reforms. In Conference "Innovative ideas in improving chemistry, food and chemical technologies", NamMTI.
7. Roxatoy Mamajanovna Egamberdieva, Mavluda Nurdinovna Khusanova, Zoxida Sharifjanovna Usmanova. TRAINING OF SMALL SPECIALISTS IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*. Vol 10, Issue 5, May, 2021.786-789. DOI 10.5958/2278-4853.2021.00483.3